

Editorial

The 75th Human Rights Day O 75º Dia Internacional dos Direitos Humanos

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In 1948, the General Assembly of the United Nations endorsed the Universal Declaration of the Human Rights. As consequence, the Human Rights Day became a celebration on the 10th of December. The promise established 75 years ago, strived for equality, freedom and justice for all.

There are reasons to celebrate, of course, but despite the evident progress made throughout the years, human beings face continuous challenges in the form of war and disparities. Social, cultural, political and religious differences between nations led to the death of young minds that were put in the front line to combat their equals, without knowing how similar there were in fact. New generations of students became a new generation of soldiers and with an increasing list of missing persons that persists at this very moment, the bright future of nations start darkening worldwide.

Forensic Science, as part of this scenario, has evolved as a candle light to assure especial Human Rights, namely the Right to Life, Liberty, and Personal Security; the Right of Freedom from Slavery; the Right of Freedom from Torture and Degrading Treatment; the Right to Recognition as a Person before the Law; the Right to be Considered Innocent until Proven Guilty; the Right to Asylum in other Countries from Persecution; the Right to Social Security among others.

When identifying the deceased becomes the utmost task during and after war, Forensic Anthropology stands out as the sentinel of the unknown. Forensic experts are aware of their importance as interpreters of a language that only a few are skilled to understand. Is their duty to

translate the signs of the body into identity. This way, the living will have closure and the deceased dignity.

Perceiving our position in space is fundamental to make our services more useful over time. The BJFA&LM compiles the technical aspects of Forensic Anthropology and Legal Medicine and delivers high-quality information so we can celebrate a little more another Human Rights Day with knowledge. Readers have free and open access to our database and are encouraged to submit their own work in order to share experience as an academic community. Bridging professionals dedicated to police units and those dedicated to research, BJFA&LM has found a way to contribute to the promotion of Human Rights.

As a forensic expert, reader, and cornerstone in the process of bringing Justice for all, what are your reasons to celebrate the upcoming Human Rights Day?

We hope that the following papers will inspire your routine.

Cordially,

Ademir Franco

Editor-in-chief